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Polygamy and Marital Infidelity: An Exploration of Amma Darko's *Not Without Flowers*

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Abstract:

This article aims to analyse Amma Darko's *Not Without Flowers* (2005), as a critical commentary on polygamy and marital adultery. It demonstrates how Amma Darko broadens her theme by offering depictions of a variety of emerging socioeconomic issues in male dominated African countries. The paper also explores the manner in which African female authors try to challenge and subvert the patriarchal traditions that persist in their nations. It highlights Darko's use of fictional prose to explore the complexity of a Ghanaian woman's life in connection to the African tradition of polygamy and its repercussions. She discusses societal evils such as adultery and polygamy, gently advising her female characters to reject these practices and critically examine the idea of the new woman, particularly in the context of modern-day Africa. Consistent with Amma Darko, the study uses a sociological approach to emphasise this aspect as a crucial reality in situations where men predominate. The novel's textual analysis, critical review and extensive research are used to examine the impact of polygamy on women in Ghana and on the African civilisation. Ultimately, she identifies

poverty and illiteracy as the primary causes of the issue. This article examines the phenomenon's roots and analyses its impact on the African community, young people and the women in question.

Keywords: Culture, fantasy, infidelity, polygamy, patriarchy, sex.

1. Introduction

Numerous authors like Buchi Emecheta, Zukiswa Wanner, Mariama Ba, Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, NoViolet Bulawayo, among others (both African and non-African), have written on women's experiences. In her autobiography, "I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings," Maya Angelou writes: "There is no greater agony than bearing an untold story inside you" (Angelou, 1969, p.198). Many authors have written extensively about the hardships and lives of African women, usually based upon and reflective of their own experiences. The African woman has faced numerous challenges that work against her "being", as she navigates the complex cycles of life, imposed upon her from childhood to adulthood, by the society. In being a harsh social reality of their lives, polygamy has a detrimental effect on the majority of African women by binding them to hardships. In some African societies, polygamy may be viewed as good when it meets a critical need, such as a household's desire for a child: but if not handled carefully, it can also backfire. There is a need to pay closer attention to the growing problems of polygamy and illegal relationships, since they are among the leading causes of marriage breakup and the key drivers of the HIV/AIDS epidemic that spreads through sexual activity.

Not Without Flowers (2007) explores the connections between men and women in African society. The author uses her imagination to highlight the difficulty of dealing with current societal issues such as polygamy and marital infidelity in declining marriages in Ghanaian culture. The narrator's personal experiences in Africa serve as an inspiration for her fictional narratives, which typically centre on the plight of women. She uses everyday

experiences to demonstrate women's status in the polygamous Ghanaian society. The primary reasons for social evils like polygamy and marital adultery in partnerships include poverty, patriarchy, passion and sexual fantasies. This research, however, delves further into the murky depths of cultural norms where HIV, childlessness, poverty, sexual exploitation, polygamy and motherhood deprive many African women of genuine happiness. This essay examines the confusions and corrupted morals that exist in modern Ghanaian society regarding the relationships between African men and women. These topics are discussed to provide readers with Amma Darko's point of view while also shedding light on unresolved concerns such as whether males are solely accountable for everything. This study employs gender analysis and the socio-criticism theoretical framework for analysis.

2. Causes of the practice

Several factors contribute to "polygamy and marital infidelity in relationships" in African societies. One of the primary causes is our male-dominated society (patriarchy), which discreetly allows men to dominate women while preventing them from expressing opposing views. *Chimamanda N. Adichie* describes how misinterpretations and misconceptions can result from a single story in this way. In her renowned TEDGlobal *The Danger of a Single Story* address in July 2009, Adichie emphasises "the complexity and diversity of the human experience by urging readers to seek out and listen to different points of view".

2.1 Patriarchy

Patriarchy in African societies manifests through various cultural, social and economic structures that traditionally position men in dominant roles. It enables men to hold key positions of political power, social privilege and property control. It gives males the option to take on as many wives as they can manage. Chinua Achebe's male character Okonkwo in *Things Fall*

Apart (1958), is portrayed as one of the Ibo tribe's most powerful men due to his numerous wives, children and accomplishments. Okonkwo is revered and feared in his tribe. This quotation elucidates this statement clearly as:

“In Okonkwo’s patriarchal society, social advancement is attained through personal achievements or merits. Thus, any less successful individual, lagging behind, is pigeonholed as “a woman by Okonkwo”.

(Achebe, p. 21)

This exemplifies Ujowundu's gender inequality philosophy, which claims that a variety of rituals and traditions contribute to women's oppression and marginalisation (2013). According to this analysis, Amma Darko's contribution to fiction writing has only served to highlight the problems that African women encounter in patriarchal societies and to empower them. She takes on patriarchy, which lies at the core of the inequality that women face in society. We saw from reading the novel that the author positively represented her female characters as they attempted to question and oppose the dominant patriarchal ideals and break norms. The female characters in the novel are strong and unwilling to be used as scapegoats for any social norm. The author portrays them as helpless objects of patriarchy, social conventions and gently advise her female characters to confront these practices.

The author portrays polygamy as an example of men's egotistical control over women and their avarice. The Pesewa’s first wife's expression of anguish upon learning about the second wife exemplifies the suffering that women face when forced to bow to men's dominance in this way. She prayed as if she were communicating to God directly:

“... Please God, expand my endurance so that I can bear the pain of his want for this other woman to whom he has legitimize his right to

desire, so that as I promised before all who once gathered....” (Darko, p. 271-272)

The above prayer of the Pesewa’s first wife vividly conveys the inner turmoil, emotional suffering, and forced submission that women endure in patriarchal societies especially within polygamous marriages where male desire is legitimized while female pain is silenced. As a woman born into an African traditional community inherits its values, which are conveyed to her throughout her life via a number of methods. Socialisation processes sustain acquired behaviours and attitudes, which are not "naturally" innate values. The well-known Pesewa serves as an excellent example in the story. The author portrays the male role, Pesewa, as a native cliché who has been faithful to several women. The following lines describe Pesewa’s character in the novel:

“lucky fellow. Sixty, plus; filthy rich; multiple wives; good life! No concubines though; lovers’ girlfriends, chicken-soups, concubines”
(Darko, P. 57).

The above lines offer a sharp critique of patriarchal privilege and the normalized entitlement of wealthy men like Pesewa in Ghanaian society. It suggests how society views men like Pesewa as fortunate for being able to indulge in wealth, multiple wives, and sexual freedoms. The author uses this tone to critique a social system that praises male promiscuity and power while overlooking the emotional and social consequences for the women involved. His wealth allows him to maintain multiple wives and exert control, reinforcing how economic status sustains gender hierarchies. The term “*chicken-soups*” likely serves as a metaphor for women who offer comfort or convenience, trivializing their identities and agency. This emphasizes how men like Pesewa commodify and consume women in various forms, often with societal approval.

2.2 Lack of Money and the Emotional Fallout

Polygamy is a by-product of the social, economic, cultural and financial issues. Large families are havens of economic power in several African societies. Several women and kids can help with farming, housework and other revenue-generating endeavours. This increases agricultural productivity and simplifies childcare and home tasks, allowing the family to live together more successfully. It can function as a tool for wealth management and consolidation. Particularly, wealthy men may take many wives as a display of their wealth and social standing. This strategy can help with the effective distribution and management of family resources. Marriage into a polygamous household can provide women in polygamous communities with financial security, especially in settings where single women have fewer options for financial independence. The novel's female character Aggie, who turns to prostitution to support her family, represents the extreme measures individuals take to live in the face of poverty. Another prominent female character, Randa, is motivated mostly by greed. She is associated with Idan because she wants to assure a comfortable lifestyle and monetary prosperity.

According to the author, the underlying causes of this situation in Africa are emotional fallout and economic hardship. The majority of African female writers portray polygamy in a way that is detrimental to women. They believe that polygamy is a realistic option for marriage. However, in addition to this bad image, the author offers a more positive aspect of polygamy. For her, polygamy is not necessarily bad for women because it allows them to have children, provide for their families and get emotional and financial support. For example, in the novel, the fifth wife enters into a polygamous relationship because she needs emotional and financial support, connection and does not want to start a family. Having many spouses can help one another emotionally and psychologically, especially while navigating the social expectations associated with having children. The polygamous partnership between Ntifor and his wives overcomes the problem of childlessness. Panyin conceals her infertility and rejoices in her co-

wife's children because one of the rules of polygamy specifies that the offspring of such a relationship belong to all spouses.

2.3 Lust and Sexual Fantasies

A common African proverb states that constantly tasting the same "soup," "meal," or "thing" is monotonous and exhausting. These are all intended to mock African women. Certain guys then search for alternative girls and intense pleasures in order to avoid a boring relationship. It describes circumstances in which males consider or perceive women as more of sexual objects than as whole individuals with desires, agency and autonomy of their own. For example, the character Idan exploits Randa for his sex fantasies in a way that emphasises the complicated and frequently difficult aspects of their relationship. Despite being married, Idan gets involved with a younger woman named Randa. Instead of being motivated by genuine affection and respect, Idan's lust and want drive their relationship. Idan views Randa as something to be objectified, mostly using her to satisfy his erotic desires. His interactions with her demonstrate this objectification, as he puts his self-fulfilment over her emotional needs and sense of autonomy. Men who grasp opportunities, such as the fictitious Idan, would utilise any situation to entice their victims. In the moment recounted by the author, Idan and his victim are in the car, looking for a chance to talk and make physical touch. The following depicts Idan and his Randa's pleasant coexistence:

“The young lady smiled. She still didn't say anything (...). The young lady saw his irritation. She laughed slightly (...) She shrugged (and said) ‘If a young female is not looking for a long-term affair, why not go in for one with the lowest risk of such an expectation?’” (Darko, p. 78)

Furthermore, the themes in Amma Darko's work reveal the various causes and socioeconomic forces that underlie characters' passion and fantasies. Idan and other characters have unmet ambitions in their marriages, which pushes them to look for fulfilment elsewhere. This is clear from Idan's connection with Randa, where unfulfilled emotional and physical demands in his marriage fuel his passion. The narrator also discusses how African women seek marriage with wealthy men to achieve financial stability through the character Randa. She's a young woman who starts hanging out with Idan. She usually utilises her beauty and charm to enter into partnerships with wealthy men because she is ambitious and seeks financial stability.

In addition to the benefits listed above, it frequently provides a break from the routine and stress of daily living. The conflict between conventional wisdom and contemporary living is a topic the narrator frequently addresses. While the younger characters are constantly divided between tradition and modernity, Mama Orojo, Aggie's mother, represents adherence to traditional values. These fantasies offer a fleeting sense of freedom and repression to the protagonists coping with stresses from both their personal and professional lives.

Many female protagonists in the novel have extramarital relationships for a variety of reasons that are inextricably linked to their social, psychological and emotional situations. For example, Pesewa's second wife believes her spouse has emotionally abandoned her. Being an influential and affluent guy, Pesewa is frequently occupied with his social and professional responsibilities. The second wife feels abandoned and unappreciated as a result of this neglect, leading her to seek emotional satisfaction elsewhere. Personal discontent and misery are significant factors in the second wife's desire to have extramarital affairs. For lust and pleasure, men and women alike become involved in marital infidelity. A prominent illustration of this is when Pa decides to fulfil his desires with a girl young enough to be his daughter because he is dissatisfied with his marriage to Ma:

“Pa began to looking for the idea of one permanent pleasure provider. A young and attractive mistress with whom he could share and live out his sexual fantasies and cravings without shame, guilt or fear. Someone who would nurture him and with whom he could even interconnect emotionally”. (Darko, p. 330)

Pa searches the neighbourhood and eventually decides on Agnes, sometimes known as Aggie. Strangely, Aggie's displeasure and disagreement with Pa's assessment of events is conveyed passionately. Pa feels envious at times since she is so passionate about her profession. She has no responsibilities and is available with a simple clap of the fingers, so the other women are undoubtedly being taken care of by the males in need of fresh air, new flesh and fresh sex. It is the manifestation of the youthful, attractive girl's abundant energy, which the wife lacks after work. The extra time, care and response that men do not receive at home in bed from polygamy increases that energy.

The fifth woman in the novel has a secretive, different motivation for marrying Pesewa a man with four wives and numerous children. The following lines depict the fifth wife's motive for polygamous marriage:

“She was in secondary school and had fallen head over heel in love with a fellow student. Their first unprotected sex got her pregnant. She was shocked. How could that have happened? (...) Then something inexplicable happened during the surgery. Instead of severing the one fallopian tube in which the fetus was developing, both were severed. She only found this out several years later. She had no idea why that happened”. (Darko, p. 261)

This passage from the novel reveals a poignant and complex motivation behind the fifth wife's decision to marry Pesewa, a wealthy polygamist. Unlike the other wives, her choice is not driven by material comfort or societal pressure alone but is deeply rooted in personal trauma and a quest for emotional closure. The author portrays Pesewa's first wife in a unique and exceptional way. Despite becoming the first, she has accepted Pesewa's mansion without any complaints from the other four wives. The author is now dehumanising polygamy, as she has with prior lovers. As soon as the other wives enter his mansion, Pesewa dumps the first wife. Rather than retaliating, the woman falls silent, shows patience and accepts Pesewa's newfound intimacy. She promotes the ideal of the moral woman that the patriarchal society expects all women to possess. The author intends to demonstrate that some women are willing to suffer the burden of humiliation and misery in a male-dominated environment.

3. The Repercussions of Marital Adultery and Polygamy

Both men and women mistakenly engage in polygamy for sexual pleasure and other social standards; the majority of Ghanaian females who are involved in polygamous marriages with older, wealthier men are unaware of the risks or adverse outcomes they may face. Additionally, females drawn to males who are virtually a mismatch for them and who in no way take on the responsibilities of their wives due to peer pressure, cultural impositions, traditional norms, their socioeconomic living standards and school amenities end up in polygamy. It can cause complex emotional dynamics inside the family, including feelings of neglect or isolation among spouses and children, as well as competition and jealousy. It is clear that each of these probable causes has devastating consequences.

3.1 Emotional Unrest and Delusional State

Polygamy places a heavy emotional strain on the individuals involved. For instance, the husband of the fictional Aggie, who is accustomed to answering calls in front of his wife,

has begun acting suspiciously when speaking with one of his numerous casual partners; he is constantly on the lookout:

“Idan rose like a zombie from the armchair. Aggie’s upper body jerked. She knew the ritual. She watched him. He strode to the bedroom for his mobile phone. Leaving it there was also part of the ritual. (...). Because if the mobile phone was beside him in the living room, where the landline was and upon the signal, he proceeded to the bedroom to make the call, it would look suspicious”. (Darko, p. 105).

Idan plays several adultery games, which creates a "catch-me-if-you-can" mentality that causes emotional instability and hallucinations in the family. Things go worse as Aggie:

“Plunged her hand back into the soapy water and brought out the first item she got hold of. Fate could be cruel, for yet again, in her hands, were Idan’s underpants. She wondered. Had he ever worn that and removed it to make love to Randa and put it back on and brought it back home with the scent of their lovemaking, for her to wash?” (Darko, p. 106)

The above lines powerfully illustrate the psychological and emotional turmoil caused by polygamy and infidelity, particularly from the perspective of the wife, Aggie. Through these lines, the author explores the subtle and destructive ways in which emotional betrayal masked under societal tolerance for polygamy and male privilege deeply affects women’s mental well-being and sense of self.

The author employs stereotypes of elderly women to emphasise the psychological element she wants the readers to notice. Idan’s grandmother, portrayed as having prophetic foresight, senses impending doom and wishes to perform a ritual to avert misfortune. Her spiritual intuition is rooted in cultural traditions that respect the wisdom and insight of elders.

However, modern scepticism and family dynamics particularly the nephew's branding of her as a witch render her powerless and alienated. The decision to exclude her from the wedding reflects how older women can become scapegoats for family anxieties and societal misfortunes, despite their often-well-meaning intentions. The inevitable happens as described in the following lines:

“On their wedding day, the pair kills and knocks down a boy. A tragedy befalls the couple years after their marriage; they are unable to conceive and face additional problems” (Darko, p. 166).

The above lines highlight the tension between traditional belief systems and modernity, while also exploring the psychological marginalization of elderly women in Ghanaian society. In the end, childlessness and the deadly HIV cause the couple's marriage to collapse. The author then challenges society to demonstrate how premonition affects women psychologically. The novel's older women's premonitions depict their elevated levels of worry and depression. Chronic stress and despondency can result from the ongoing dread of betrayal and the reality of sharing a partner.

Another reason why women commonly have hallucinations during the aforementioned situation might be explored in the novel. Women have few channels in society to voice their emotions. Men are permitted by society to hang out with friends, drink beer and make approaches to women. African women do not have access to such changes. Married women are not expected to spend their stressful days seeking solace and amusement outside the home, unlike their male counterparts. Consequently, the married lady has very tiny way to express her annoyance. The author suggests that women's hallucinations are caused by the accumulation of daily stress. When this occurs, they are accused of being insane or witches. In the novel, Ma and other female characters find themselves in this situation.

3.2 Infidelity in Relationships and Prostitution

In the novel, second wife Aggie and Randa engage in "sugar daddy/mummy," a type of prostitution in which a very young man or female dates elderly, often married, male or female. In exchange for the elderly man or woman's emotional and material support, the young girl/boy gives them sex. Desire for materialistic lives forces women to discover ways to support themselves financially. Prostitution, usually involving an adult and financially stable person or female known as the "sugar daddy/mummy," is preferred when there are no other respectable options.

The author shows that prostitution is not beneficial to women in any manner. She claims that prostitution does not provide women with a "safety valve," but somewhat limits them by labelling those who are not chaste "whores." For example, "people stop gossiping about prostitutes as soon as Randa enters Ma Cherie's hairdressing salon because they know her as being in a sexual affair with Idan, a married man" (Darko, 2007, p. no.292-97). Furthermore, Pesewa's second wife becomes apathetic, suppresses her jealousy and pays attention to her evil inner voice as she plans to become a prostitute herself. Throughout the novel, the author shows that people engage in prostitution for a several reasons, including financial security and unmet sexual dreams with their spouses. A man cannot please as many women sexually as he would want at once, as Pesewa and his second marital link demonstrate. As a result, the second wife's libido is satiated and she starts looking for other men. Pesewa's second wife does not face financial difficulties. She turns to prostitution as a kind of dominance to further her career and satisfy her sexual cravings with her partners. The novel reveals that she is not getting the same amount of sexiness and thrill from her partner as she does with other young men. The conventions of polygamy motivate the female prostitutes. The scenario explores that the majority of women who engage in prostitution have little control over who they work for or how much money they earn.

Through her female characters, the author examines how women are often pushed into prostitution by both overt and hidden forces. For financial reasons, Aggie starts dating a married man as well as a regular lover, whom she eventually marries. The second wife's subtle power of marital dissatisfaction drives her to become involved in prostitution. Randa has a study boyfriend, but she also has a subliminal power that drives her: a desire for retribution. Large cities are the precise location where prostitution takes place in Darko's text. Women in the city utilise their bodies as commodities and are treated with disrespect by the public. Because there are fewer opportunities for education and employment in cities, women may be driven into prostitution. The novel focuses on the social and economic causes that drive people into prostitution, as well as the role of the sugar daddy/mummy.

3.3 Polygamous Infidelity and Sexual Disease

Although polygamous marriage is thought to shield women from societal injustice and other negative influences, it increases the risk of HIV infection in their lifetime. Infidelity in marriage and polygamy are significant factors in the spread of HIV in men and women. The novel explores the complexities of interpersonal interactions and societal norms in Ghana, focussing on how individual acts and cultural practices contribute to the virus's spread. Due to the various sexual partners in a marriage, the practice of polygamy which is culturally acceptable in some parts of Ghana increases the risk of HIV transmission. In the novel, men who take on more wives or have numerous wives without giving the health consequences enough thought to endanger all of their partners. Due to the interdependence of sexual connections, HIV can spread quickly among members of a polygamous group if one person is infected. Nancy Luke points out that "several studies that examine the association between age differences and unsafe sexual behaviour and sexual diseases define a large age difference as ten or more years and others use a five-year cutoff" (2001). According to this, older men who pay for sexual urges with gifts, cash, or by paying for school fees are more likely to be HIV

positive. It is the circumstance involving Pesewa, Pa and Idan in the focus narrative. For instance, it is revealed that characters with numerous wives, like Agya Ntifor and Pesewa, are more likely to get illnesses and spread them because of their frequent sexual encounters. Examining Pesewa's connections with his several wives is the main way to study polygamy. By balancing his responsibilities and relationships with each of his wives, Pesewa illuminates the difficulties in a polygamous marriage. Every wife offers a different viewpoint on the polygamous relationship. The subtleties of their everyday married life are shown via their individual tales and interactions with Pesewa and one another.

Darko investigates the moral and ethical implications of adultery through her characters, such as Pesewa and his several wives. The author investigates the causes of adultery in marriage, including emotional deprivation, social pressures and personal discontent. She draws attention to the low rate of condom use in polygamous relationships, which is caused partially by societal attitudes and partially by marital trust. This lack of protection contributes to the spread of sexual disease. She also looks at the power relationships in polygamous marriages, which frequently give women little control over negotiating safe sex practices. This imbalance is exemplified by situations in the novel when ladies are afraid to demand safe sex practices for fear of losing status or favour with their husbands. Women have no control over protected sex, as stated in the following lines:

“Ah! What is the world coming to? Did you hear her? If the man refused to wear a condom, she wore one. Ei! This is all the fault of those too known white women in Europe and America. All they need are a few crazy educated Ghanaian women who think more white than black in their black skins. But I don't blame them. It's the white people. They started it all. They made the condoms for us, made the power we had over whether to wear it or not, get into our heads; then boom,

dropped another for the women too. Just to undermine our power. So now if we refuse to wear it, our women just excuse themselves into the bathroom. And if you think that she went in there to urinate, think again. By the time she returns to bed, she has it in place. E! what is the world coming to?". (Darko, p. 89)

The novel illustrates the role that extramarital affairs have in the transmission of STDs and HIV/AIDS. Characters have extramarital affairs, frequently without protection, which raises the possibility that the virus will re-enter their main relationships. Agya Ntifor's infidelity is shown as a significant source of infection, putting his wives and, consequently, their children in danger in addition to himself. The intricacies of adultery inside Randa and Idan's marriage are revealed through a thorough and nuanced exploration of their relationship. One of the key elements of their relationship is Idan's extramarital encounters. The author also explores how Idan's adultery undermines Randa's confidence and the soundness of their union. Infidelity is not just a male trait; women also commit this offence occasionally in reaction to their husbands' behaviour and other times because of personal preferences and external factors. Darko explores themes of betrayal, autonomy and polygamous marriage through the figure of Pesewa's fifth wife. The issue is made worse by a lack of trust and communication between partners, which discourages people from seeking help and testing or disclosing their infidelity. Darko offers a fascinating examination of the complications of marital infidelity and its emotional fallout through the relationship between men and women.

4. Conclusion

This essay tries to demonstrate that tackling male-oriented practices in African communities is necessary in order to address the problems of polygamy and marital infidelity. Amma Darko raises a similar voice, pleading with Ghana and other African nations to take

action to protect African women from these cultural practices. She persuasively makes points that look at the conventions around polygamy and marital adultery and how they affect African men and women. For the past thirty years, a large portion of feminist writing has been shaped and directed by ideas about gender and gender-related concerns. Writers such as Amma Darko created the narration of Ghanaian social realities. Infidelity in marriage and polygamy can lead to many social risks that affect society's social dynamics, general health and wellbeing of the person. Therefore, the primary goal of female writers like Amma Darko in her novel is to combat the aforementioned social concerns. She, like many other African female writers, portrays social difficulties in that spectrum of thought as the fundamental components impeding the advancement of African women in a society controlled by men. Amma Darko's hobbies, character and critical point of view about the patriarchal belief that acknowledges as superior to women and views women as sex commodities have all been clarified by this paper. The dedicated female novelist proposes the beginning and development of a new era in women's fiction that is, writing about and by women. Their phenomenon represents a literary movement that seeks to uncover and expose societal injustices against women via the presenting of subjects. The author uses her fiction to empower women, hence raising awareness of women's issues throughout her approach. Finally, this study found that marital infidelity and polygamy are the primary obstacles inhibiting African women's social wellbeing.

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